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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D5.4 TAM Prototype Model

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Abstract:	D5.4 is a report on the first iteration of technology acceptance modelling (TAM), which focuses on developing a structural equation model (SEM) capable of accurately predicting travellers' acceptance of smart border control technologies.
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Terms and abbreviations

Terms:

BC	Border Control
BCP	Border Control Point
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EES	European Union Entry/Exit System
SBC	Smart Border Control
SEM	Structural Equation Modeling
SOTA	State of the Art
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model/Modelling
TCN	Third-Country Nationals
TCNVE	Third-Country Nationals Visa Exempt
TCNVH	Third-Country Nationals Visa Holders
UTAUT	Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
BI	Behavioral Intention
IDV	Individualism versus Collectivism
NN	Neural Network
ML	Machine Learning
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
M	Mean
SD	Standard Deviation
CI	Confidence interval
t	t statistic
CoD	Coefficient of Determination ($=R^2$)
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
AVE	Average Variance Extracted
α	Cronbach's α
ρ_c	composite reliability coefficient
ρ_A	consistent reliability coefficient
FL	Fornell-Larcker (criterion for validity)

Feature names:

CO	Collectivism
DISCRIM	Previous experience with discrimination
EC	Expected convenience
EDU	Education level
EEOU	Expected ease of use
EIHW	Expected impact on health and well-being
EIOP	Expected impact on privacy
GIT	General interest in technology

LTO	Long-term orientation
MA	Masculinity
PD	Power distance
PE	Performance expectancy
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
PITAD	Perceived influence on border control technologies on anti-discrimination
PSBC	Previous smart border control experience
PTE1	Travel frequency (within the EU)
PTE2	Travel frequency (outside of the EU)
PTE3	Travel frequency (with children)
PTE4	Travel frequency (business trips)
TECH	Technology type
TIA	Trust in border control authority
TIPT	Trust in particular technology
UA	Uncertainty avoidance

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the first iteration of the METICOS WP5 technology acceptance modeling (TAM), which focuses on traveler acceptance of smart border control technologies. Using the traveler TAM dataset presented in D5.3, a model was developed that is capable of accurately explaining as well as predicting traveler acceptance of a given border control technology. To this end, the PLS-SEM (partial least squares structural equation modeling) approach was chosen, because of its advantages over traditional covariance-based SEM.

Benchmarking and comparison with alternative modeling approaches show, that the resulting PLS-SEM performs almost as good as traditional machine-learning based approaches in terms of accuracy (approx. 0.889 RMSE) and variance explained (approx. 72%). However, the PLS-SEM approach provides much higher levels of explainability, flexibility and extensibility, thereby representing the optimal balance between performance and explainability in the context of the METICOS project.

The resulting traveler PLS-SEM TAM model serves as the basis of the ETAP algorithm development in T5.5. Furthermore, once the border control staff survey is completed and results data analyzed (T5.2), the same modeling approach as presented here will be used for the development of the staff TAM model (D5.8).

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

Deliverable D5.4 provides an overview of the first iteration of the METICOS WP5 technology acceptance modeling (TAM), which focuses on traveler acceptance of smart border control technologies. Using the traveler TAM dataset presented in D5.3, a model is developed that is capable of accurately explaining as well as predicting traveler acceptance of a given border control technology, using the PLS-SEM (partial least squares structural equation modeling) approach. The resulting PLS-SEM model is also compared with an alternative, machine-learning (ML) based reference model in order to better understand its performance and selection of features. The resulting model will serve as the basis of the ETAP algorithm development in T5.5.

1.2 Document structure

After this introduction, Section 2 describes the modelling goals and requirements, e.g., aiming for high model quality and explainability. Furthermore, the resulting model should be aligned with existing literature to provide a meaningful scientific contribution to technology acceptance-related theories and models in the context of border and access control. In Section 3, a short overview about the input data is provided and the general data preparation and cleaning is explained.

After that, in Section 4 the development of METICOS TAM model prototype is described in detail. First, a short overview about underlying theoretical acceptance models is given and how they are applied in various contexts. Second, various modelling techniques are described, i.e., regression modelling, structural equation modelling and partial least squares structural equation modelling. In Section 4.2, the analytical approach is described, e.g., splitting the dataset in one set for training and one set for comparison. After that, in Section 4.3 the generated models are described in detail. First, the initial model “PLS model 1” is explained and specific model reliability and validity. Finally, path coefficients and explainability of the first model is provided. Based on the evaluation of our first model, a less complex model was conceived, labelled as “PLS model 2”. Similar to the first model, model reliability, validity path coefficients and explainability is provided for the second model. In the following Section 4.4, the resulting model is interpreted.

In Section 5, the results of the training and evaluation of an alternative, machine-learning (ML) based reference model that is supposed to complement the main (PLS-SEM based) model are discussed. Model development on behalf of XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is explained and the results of the modelling process are discussed and interpreted. Finally, Section 5 compares the PLS SEM models from Section 4 to the reference model with the goal to obtain a better understanding of their performance and identify eventual deviations in terms of e.g., key features used for prediction.

In Section 6, it is explained which model was finally chosen for further model deployment tasks and the handling of potential biases in model and dataset is discussed. Finally, the last Section 7 provides conclusions and finalize the deliverable.

2 Modeling Goals and Requirements

In the previous deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 the empirical ground truth data collection and analysis on how travelers in European cities evaluate certain smart border technologies is discussed. By means of various modelling approaches – discussed in this deliverable - this data is used to develop predictive models that are supposed to fulfill three main goals: first, the resulting model should have high model quality, e.g., high accuracy, little overfitting/variance, etc. Secondly, the resulting model should be able to explain how acceptance of border control technologies is determined by several user- and technology related factors, i.e., high explanatory power and transparency is crucial.

Furthermore, the resulting model should be aligned with existing literature (see Section 4.1.1) to provide a meaningful scientific contribution to technology acceptance-related theories and models in the context of border and access control. This requires structural equation modeling (SEM) as starting point and avoid approaches like neuronal networks because they tend to result in “black boxes” which does not show the impact of certain factors on acceptance prediction or reflect any theory. As required by task T5.5, the created models discussed in this deliverable are ready for further updates or modifications to maintain prediction accuracy and validity of the acceptance model also in the future. This includes efficient mechanisms to a) manually update the model with new data and expert knowledge as well as b) to automatically recalibrate the model by using the data provided by the METICOS platform itself.

3 Modeling Dataset

3.1 Input Data

For modelling the traveler TAM, we used the main traveler survey data set, which is described in detail in deliverable D5.3. This dataset is based on 8010 filled out questionnaires, 1600 samples/responses for each of the five evaluated border control technologies (3D face recognition, e-Gate, fingerprint, face recognition, passport scanner). For further information on the content of this dataset, please refer to deliverable D5.2. A list of variable mappings to survey questions can be found in Annex 2 of deliverable D5.3.

3.2 Data Preparation and Cleaning

This subsection describes the general preparation of the data needed to arrive at the modeling dataset use for training and testing the SEMs and other models. The primary data collected for technology acceptance modeling consists of questionnaire-based surveys. Thus, data preprocessing in this case has the main goal of transforming raw survey response data into modeling or analysis datasets of sufficient quality. This preprocessing was performed in three steps:

1. Removal of incomplete records: if responses for non-optional questionnaire items are missing, the respective record were removed.
2. Removal of invalid responses and outliers: if records contain ostensibly invalid responses and/or exhibit suspicious rating behavior (e.g., variance of rating scores very close to zero), the respective record were removed.
3. In additional, derived variables (such as TAM factors derived from single items) were calculated and added to the dataset (as additional columns).

Following the preprocessing steps described above, the final dataset used for traveler TAM modelling consists of 7639 samples.

4 Development of METICOS TAM model prototype

4.1 Background: Evolution of TAM and SEM

4.1.1 Application and Modification of Acceptance Models

Before providing insights how the empirical data was used to model acceptance of smart border technologies in upcoming chapters, a short overview about underlying theoretical acceptance models is given. Several approaches exist to describe how users evaluate a certain technology to estimate its utility and to finally determine if this technology is acceptable. The Theory of Reasonable Action by Fishbein and Ajzen [1] is one of the oldest models used to predict acceptance. It includes different kind of beliefs and subjective norms to determine behavioral intention to use a certain technology. Based on this concept, Ajzen [2] extended it and developed Theory of Planned Behavior which is about one factor that determines behavioral intention of the person's attitudes toward that behavior. Finally, the first Technology Acceptance Model was introduced by Davis [3]. An adaptation of Theory of Reasonable Action, TAM is specifically tailored for modeling users' acceptance of information systems or technologies. The basic TAM model included and tested two specific beliefs: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). Perceived Usefulness is defined as the potential user's subjective likelihood that the use of a certain system will improve his/her action and Perceived Ease of Use refers to the degree to which the potential user expects the target system to be effortless. This first TAM was further extended and improved, which resulted in TAM 2 [4] and TAM 3 [5]. The authors developed the TAM 3 using the four different types including the individual differences, system characteristics, social influence, and facilitating conditions which are determinants of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The latest revision of the theory of technology acceptance model resulted in Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) [6]. The UTAUT has four predictors of users' behavioral intention: Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions. The five similar constructs including perceived usefulness, extrinsic motivation, job-fit, relative advantage and outcome expectations form the performance expectancy in the UTAUT model while effort expectancy captures the notions of perceived ease of use and complexity. For a detailed overview about the various versions of acceptance model and for a comparison, please see [7].

Literature shows that TAM has been applied in various contexts and scenarios. For nearly any technology, one can find an acceptance evaluation using empirical data to explain acceptability from an end user's perspective. For example, in [8] the authors introduce the virtual reality hardware acceptance model VR-HAM via extending and individualizing the technology acceptance model for virtual reality hardware. Similar to this, in [9] the authors developed and evaluated VR TAM, which includes variables from the TAM, user experience, variables specific to VR, and variables relating to user characteristics. In the context of biometrics, the authors of [10] introduced the Unified TAM on biometrics and in the context of voice recognition model, an empirical extension of the technology acceptance model is presented [16]. For a detailed overview about various application of acceptance models in various contexts (e.g., telemedicine, digital library system, e-learning, etc.) please see [11].

In [11] it is also shown, that in most of acceptance modelling research, TAM (or its successor) has been adapted and/or modified to be applicable in certain contexts. Hence, core concepts of TAM (e.g., impact of easiness of use and usefulness on intention to use) are extended with new, context-specific factors. For example, in [8] the authors added the factors "Willingness to pay" and "Curiosity" and in [12] the authors added the factors "Interaction", "Immersion" and "Imagination" to describe the acceptability of a virtual reality system in medical education. Hence, in research it is commonly

accepted, that modified acceptance models are used, which are adapted to fit a certain application context.

Hence, in METICOS we use an adapted and customized acceptance model, which is shown in the Figure below (see also deliverable D5.1 for further details).

Figure 1: METICOS TAM Model Framework.

4.1.2 TAM and Regression Modelling

As described in D5.2 “Technology Acceptance User Survey Results”, online surveys had been conducted to collect empirical data about acceptance and smart border control technologies. This data is used to explain which factors impact the acceptance of these border technologies in a quantitative way. To describe the quantitative relationship between relevant acceptance factors, different approaches are available like correlation analysis, regression modelling, structural equation modelling (SEM) or machine learning (ML) techniques. For example, in [13] multivariate regression analysis is used to explain the acceptance of computerized accounting systems and in [14] simple correlation analysis is used to determine acceptance of simulation tools for teaching assistants. In contrast to more advanced methods like SEM or ML, even these simple techniques provide valuable insights to understand technology acceptance.

However, there are undeniable disadvantages when such basic methods are applied. In [18], the authors state three main limitations. First, an over-simplified model structure (i.e., several independent variables, one dependent variable) is postulated. Of course, omitting some aspect of reality [15] is necessary, regression-based approaches may be too limiting for an analysis of more complex and more realistic situations. For example, it is not possible to consider the situation, in which dependent variables influence other dependent variables. Second, regression analysis treats all variables as observable. Direct observable variables are for example sex and gender. But in our case,

most variables are created based on various questionnaire items, which classifies them as non-directly observable (i.e., latent constructs). Strictly speaking, the inclusion of latent constructs in a quantitative model requires prior stand-alone validation (e.g., using confirmatory factor analysis) [16]. Third, first generation regression analysis only provides correct results, if there is no systematic or random measurement error [17], which is highly unlikely in real-world scenarios. To properly take into account systematic and random measurement error, more sophisticated approaches are needed (e.g., SEM).

4.1.3 TAM and SEM

To overcome these limitations of first-generation techniques, more and more authors started using structural equation modeling (SEM) as an alternative for acceptance modelling. For example, in [18] the authors used SEM to model the acceptance of a safety helmet reminder system for motorcyclists and in [19] the authors used structural equation modelling to model acceptance of e-learning systems in developing countries.

As written in [20], “Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a collection of statistical techniques that allow a set of relationships between one or more independent variables (IVs), either continuous or discrete, and one or more dependent variables (DVs), either continuous or discrete, to be examined. Both IVs and DVs can be either factors or measured variables. Structural equation modeling is also referred to as causal modeling, causal analysis, simultaneous equation modeling, analysis of covariance structures, path analysis, or confirmatory factor analysis”.

In general, SEM is used to evaluate if a theoretical model (e.g., technology acceptance model for a certain technology) fit with empirical observations, e.g., questionnaire results. If a model fits with empirical data, hypotheses are verified, e.g., the factor ease of use significantly influences intention to use. However, traditional covariance-based (CB) SEM also has some limitations, that’s why we use PLS-SEM in the context of acceptance modelling in the METICOS project.

4.1.4 TAM and PLS-SEM: Explanatory vs. Predictive Modeling

PLS-SEM is an alternative method to traditional CB-SEM. While it offers similar advantages as CB-SEM in comparison to first generation techniques (e.g., modelling of latent constructs, testing of complex relationships based on theoretical considerations), it addresses some of the limitations associated with CB-SEM.

Among those limitations, a key issue addressed by PLS-SEM is that CB-SEM can only be used for explanatory analysis (i.e., empirically evaluating relationships deduced from theory and logic) but not for *prediction* (i.e., using the explanatory model to make predictions on new cases) [16]. [16] summarize this essential advantage of PLS-SEM as follows:

“PLS-SEM-based model estimation and assessment follow a causal–predictive paradigm, in which the objective is to test the predictive power of a model, derived from theory and logic. As such, the method strikes a balance between machine learning methods, which are fully predictive in nature and CB-SEM, which focuses on confirmation and model fit [...]. Its causal–predictive nature makes PLS-SEM particularly appealing for research in fields that aim to derive recommendations for practice. For example, recommendations in managerial implication sections in business research journals always include predictive statements (“our results suggest that managers should...”). Making such statements requires a prediction focus on model estimation and evaluation [...]. PLS-SEM perfectly

emphasizes this need as the method sheds light on the mechanisms (i.e., the structural model relationships) through which the predictions are generated.” (p. 14)

While explanatory modelling focuses on macro-level decisions (i.e., looking at the “average case”) predictive modelling can allow for decisions for individual cases (e.g., individual persons) [21]. Thus, in practice, a well-specified PLS-SEM can predict the outcome of interest (e.g., behavioral intention to use) on new cases for which the outcome is not known. At the same time, the model can provide insight regarding factors that influence this outcome. Apart from the ability to make predictions based on a theoretically derived model, PLS-SEM offers several additional advantages. For example, PLS-SEM is robust in cases where variables are not normally distributed [16]. Moreover, because the PLS-SEM algorithm does not estimate all relationships in the structural model at once, PLS-SEM works well for relatively small sample sizes [16]. Finally, PLS-SEM is better suited for modelling of highly complex relationships (in comparison to its covariance-based counterpart) as it is less prone to identification and convergence issues and holds higher statistical power [16].

As the TAM model to develop in METICOS requires both a sound explanatory perspective as well as predictive capabilities, PLS-SEM appears to be the most suitable approach that satisfies both requirements. The additional flexibility regarding sample size, distributional assumptions and modelling of highly complex relationships makes it the appropriate choice for explaining and predicting behavioral intention to use border control technologies.

4.2 Analytical approach and data preprocessing

Before model development, the input dataset was split into a dataset for model training and a dataset for the comparison of the final PLS model with a reference model. Note that only the training set was used to train and tune the different models. After the final comparison using the test set, no further model revision was undertaken to avoid the potential risk of overfitting (i.e., the model losing its ability to perform well with new unseen data). This evaluation approach (i.e., using the training set for model training and tuning - for example using cross-validation - and finally evaluating the model on a test set but without applying any further modifications) is often recommended in the context of predictive modelling and machine learning [22].

To set aside a dataset for comparison with other models, adequate sample size required for PLS-SEM needs to be taken into account. In general, the overall complexity of the structural model only marginally influences sample size requirements for PLS-SEM [16]. A rule of thumb suggested by [23] is that the minimum sample size should equal 10 times the number of predictors (independent variables) in the most complex regression in the PLS path model. For example, a regression that includes 10 predictors should be computed based on a sample size of at least 100 cases. Another guideline called the inverse square root method was proposed by [24]. It takes into account the “probability that the ratio of a path coefficient and its standard error will be greater than the critical value of a test statistic for a specific significance level” [16]. For example, to detect significance of a path coefficient of a size ranging from 0.05 to 0.1 at a significance level of 0.05, a sample size of at least 619 cases is recommended [16].

Following these guidelines, a test set containing roughly 20% of the cases of the full dataset was created (1528 cases). The dataset for model training consists of 80% of all cases (6111 cases). Thus, the sample size of the training dataset should be sufficient to detect even small effects. Cases for the two datasets were selected at random with stratification by technology type.

Analysis was performed in R 4.1.2 [25]. Specifically, the SEMinR package [26] was used to fit and evaluate models in the PLS-SEM framework. Categorical variables (gender, education level, technology type, country) were dummy coded to be able to include them in the analysis.

Conceptually, the model development in the PLS framework was conducted in three iterative steps: First, a model including all variables hypothesized to influence BITU was fitted (PLS model 1). Based on assessment of reliability and validity for PLS model 1, constructs not fulfilling reliability or validity criteria were excluded. Second, the model without the excluded constructs was refitted and significance of path coefficients was examined (PLS model 1b). Third, based on investigation of path coefficients, a reduced, parsimonious model was computed that only includes predictors that meet reliability and validity criteria and show with a significant association with BITU (PLS model 2).

4.3 Model Development and Evaluation

4.3.1 PLS model 1 (initial model)

4.3.1.1 Conceptual description

For PLS model 1, behavioral intention to use (BITU), the outcome variable to be predicted by the model, was included as a latent construct measured by three indicators (“items”). Moreover, all variables that are hypothesized to influence the outcome variable of interest (BITU) based on the METICOS TAM model (see also deliverable D5.1) were included as predictors. Table 1 shows an overview of all exogeneous variables (“predictors”) included in PLS model 1.

Table 1. Exogeneous variables (“predictors”) included in PLS model 1.

Variable	Abbreviation	Category	Measurement model
Technology type	TECH	Technology-related characteristics	Single item
Expected ease of use	EEOU	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Expected impact on privacy	EIOP	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Expected impact on health and well-being	EIHW	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators
Performance expectancy	PE	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Trust in particular technology	TIPT	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators
Expected convenience	EC	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Perceived influence of border control technologies on anti-discrimination	PITAD	Technology-related characteristics	Single item
Collectivism	CO	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Power distance	PD	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Uncertainty avoidance	UA	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Masculinity	MA	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Long-term orientation	LTO	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators

Variable	Abbreviation	Category	Measurement model
Trust in border control authority	TIA	User characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Travel frequency (within the EU)	PTE1	User characteristics	Single item
Travel frequency (outside of the EU)	PTE2	User characteristics	Single item
Travel frequency (with children)	PTE3	User characteristics	Single item
Travel frequency (business trips)	PTE4	User characteristics	Single item
Previous smart border control experience	PSBC	User characteristics	Single item
Previous experience with discrimination	DISCRIM	User characteristics	Single item
General interest in technology	GIT	User characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with four indicators
Age	AGE	User characteristics	Single item
Sex	GENDER	User characteristics	Single item
Education level	EDU	User characteristics	Single item
Country	COUNTRY	User characteristics	Single item

Nationality and origin were not included in the model as both variables were associated with highly imbalanced sample sizes and a high number of factor levels which could potentially result in an overly complex, unreliable model. All variables presented in Table 1 were modelled with a direct relationship to behavioral intention to use. In addition, based on previous versions of the TAM [5], a relationship between EEOU and PE was included in the model. No further interrelationships between exogenous constructs were incorporated based on theoretical assumptions. Moreover, all measurements in the model are assumed to be reflective (i.e., as opposed to formative measurement), and no higher order constructs and moderations were included.

4.3.1.2 Model reliability and validity

Following [16], reliability in regard to the latent constructs was assessed based on four criteria: Cronbach's α , composite reliability (ρ_c) [27], and the consistent reliability coefficient (ρ_A) [28]. For sufficient reliability of a construct, α , ρ_c , and ρ_A should exceed a value of 0.7 [26]. Table 2 shows the different reliability coefficients by construct for PLS model 1. In summary, reliability appears to good for most constructs. However, for EHOW PD, and LTO reliability coefficients are not satisfactory.

Table 2. Reliability of constructs in PLS model 1. Single item measures omitted.

Variable	α	ρ_c	ρ_A
BITU	0.963	0.976	0.963
EEOU	0.892	0.933	0.908
PE	0.872	0.921	0.880
EC	0.933	0.957	0.936

Variable	α	ρ_c	ρ_A
TIPT	0.886	0.946	0.886
EIHW	0.163	0.111	-0.216
EIOP	0.95	0.968	0.950
TIA	0.956	0.972	0.956
GIT	0.906	0.934	0.909
CO	0.879	0.925	0.883
UA	0.909	0.943	0.911
PD	0.825	0.570	-3.375
MA	0.857	0.885	2.561
LTO	0.441	0.779	0.461

Convergent validity was assessed by inspecting the average variance extracted (AVE). According to [16], the AVE for a construct should be above 0.5 to indicate sufficient convergent validity. Moreover, the Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to examine discriminative validity [29]. The Fornell-Larcker criterion is fulfilled when the \sqrt{AVE} for a construct is higher than the highest construct correlation for this particular construct [29]. A summary of validity coefficients for PLS model 1 is presented in Table 3. Similar to the reliability assessment, convergent and discriminant validity appear to be acceptable for most constructs; however, criteria for sufficient convergent validity are violated in the cases of EIOP and PD.

Table 3. AVE and \sqrt{AVE} compared to highest construct correlations for PLS model 1. The Fornell-Larcker criterion is fulfilled when the \sqrt{AVE} for a construct is higher than the highest construct correlation for this particular construct [29].

Variable	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}	Highest correlation	Variable of highest cor.	F.-L. crit. fulfilled
BITU	0.931	0.965	0.813	EC	Yes
EEOU	0.823	0.907	0.588	EC	Yes
PE	0.796	0.892	0.837	EC	Yes
EC	0.881	0.939	0.837	PE	Yes
TIPT	0.898	0.947	0.78	EC	Yes
EIHW	0.461	0.679	0.416	PE	Yes
EIOP	0.909	0.953	0.112	DISCRIM	Yes
TIA	0.920	0.959	0.657	TIPT	Yes
GIT	0.779	0.883	0.366	CO	Yes
CO	0.805	0.897	0.401	UA	Yes
UA	0.847	0.920	0.544	EC	Yes

Variable	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}	Highest correlation	Variable of highest cor.	F.-L. crit. fulfilled
PD	0.367	0.606	0.331	MA	Yes
MA	0.723	0.850	0.331	PD	Yes
LTO	0.639	0.799	0.323	UA	Yes

Given insufficient reliability and convergent validity of EIHW, PD, and LTO, these constructs were removed from the model before further analysis (in particular, before interpreting the magnitude and significance of model paths between variables). This revised model that does not include EIHW and PD is referred to as PLS model 1b in the following.

4.3.1.3 Significance of model paths

In general, PLS model 1b explains roughly 74% of the variance in BITU. Table 4 shows bootstrapped coefficients for PLS model 1b based on 10,000 resamples. If the 95% confidence interval (CI) does not enclose 0, the respective path can be considered significant at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The bootstrapped mean (M) indicates how strongly two respective constructs are associated. In general, technology related characteristics tend to be highly correlated with BITU. In contrast, no significant link between basic demographic characteristics (in particular, gender, age, and education level) and BITU appears to exist.

Table 4. Bootstrapped coefficients for paths in the PLS model 1b (10,000 resamples).

Path	Bootstrap M	Bootstrap SD	t	95% CI
EEOU → PE*	0.566	0.012	47.141	[0.542; 0.589]
EEOU → BITU*	0.035	0.011	3.322	[0.015; 0.055]
PE → BITU*	0.169	0.018	9.646	[0.135; 0.203]
EC → BITU*	0.379	0.020	19.114	[0.340; 0.418]
TIPT → BITU*	0.171	0.016	10.658	[0.140; 0.203]
EIOP → BITU*	-0.102	0.008	-12.667	[-0.118; -0.086]
TECH_3DFACE → BITU*	-0.027	0.009	-2.877	[-0.045; -0.009]
TECH_PASSPORT → BITU*	0.063	0.008	7.894	[0.048; 0.079]
TECH_FACE → BITU*	0.007	0.009	0.770	[-0.010; 0.024]
TECH_EGATE → BITU*	0.046	0.008	5.586	[0.030; 0.062]
ATT_TECH_DISCRIM → BITU*	0.044	0.008	5.511	[0.028; 0.060]
AGE → BITU	0.010	0.007	1.435	[-0.004; 0.025]
GENDER_FEMALE → BITU	0.009	0.007	1.294	[-0.005; 0.022]
EDU_HS → BITU	-0.046	0.033	-1.383	[-0.115; 0.019]
EDU_MA → BITU	-0.048	0.033	-1.449	[-0.116; 0.016]

Path	Bootstrap <i>M</i>	Bootstrap <i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	95% <i>CI</i>
EDU_BA → BITU	-0.050	0.032	-1.596	[-0.114; 0.010]
EDU_VS → BITU	-0.042	0.024	-1.733	[-0.091; 0.005]
EDU_ES → BITU	-0.028	0.017	-1.657	[-0.063; 0.005]
EDU_PHD → BITU	-0.007	0.013	-0.553	[-0.032; 0.018]
COUNTRY_SWE → BITU*	-0.021	0.009	-2.28	[-0.039; -0.003]
COUNTRY_NOR → BITU	-0.01	0.009	-1.229	[-0.027; 0.006]
COUNTRY_ROM → BITU*	-0.046	0.010	-4.602	[-0.065; -0.026]
COUNTRY_EST → BITU*	-0.021	0.009	-2.233	[-0.039; -0.002]
COUNTRY_GRE → BITU*	-0.051	0.009	-5.508	[-0.069; -0.033]
COUNTRY_FRA → BITU	-0.014	0.009	-1.533	[-0.031; 0.004]
COUNTRY_BEL → BITU	0.001	0.009	0.078	[-0.017; 0.019]
PTE1 → BITU*	-0.031	0.015	-2.086	[-0.06; -0.002]
PTE2 → BITU	-0.004	0.022	-0.299	[-0.044; 0.054]
PTE3 → BITU	0.006	0.019	0.375	[-0.037; 0.042]
PTE4 → BITU	0.006	0.016	0.466	[-0.029; 0.033]
PSBC → BITU	0.008	0.007	1.246	[-0.005; 0.021]
TIA → BITU*	0.069	0.012	5.977	[0.046; 0.092]
GIT → BITU*	0.048	0.009	5.308	[0.030; 0.066]
DISCRIM → BITU	0.012	0.006	1.802	[-0.001; 0.024]
CO → BITU	0.014	0.009	1.482	[-0.004; 0.032]
UA → BITU*	0.030	0.011	2.777	[0.009; 0.050]
MA → BITU	0.000	0.007	0.062	[-0.015; 0.014]

Note: TECH, GENDER, EDU, and COUNTRY are dummy coded. TECH reference category: Fingerprint, GENDER reference category: Male, EDU reference category: No degree, COUNTRY reference category: Austria. *M* = mean, *SD* = standard Deviation, *t* = *t* statistic, *CI* = confidence interval. * $p < 0.05$

4.3.2 PLS model 2 (reduced, parsimonious model)

4.3.2.1 Conceptual description

Based on the evaluation of PLS model 1 and PLS model 1b, a less complex model was conceived that only includes constructs with sufficient reliability and validity and variables with a significant association with BITU. Accordingly, the following variables are excluded from Model 2 as predictors: AGE, GENDER, EDU, PSBC, PTE2-4, DISCRIM, CO and MA. Exceptions is TECH and COUNTRY for which no significant association for certain factor levels was found; however, as other factor levels are significantly associated with BITU, both variables are still included in the model.

The approach of reducing model complexity offers advantages from both an explanatory and a predictive perspective. From an explanatory perspective, PLS model 2 only includes variables with a meaningful contribution. From a predictive perspective, a model with reduced complexity is less prone to learning patterns that are specific to the training data, thus reducing the risk of overfitting. Table 5 shows all exogeneous variables included in PLS model 2. The measurement model for BITU and paths in in PLS model 2 were not altered compared to previous model versions.

Table 5. Exogeneous variables included in PLS model 2.

Variable	Abbreviation	Category	Measurement model
Technology type	TECH	Technology-related characteristics	Single item
Expected ease of use	EEOU	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Expected impact on privacy	EIOP	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Performance expectancy	PE	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators
Trust in particular technology	TIPT	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators
Expected convenience	EC	Technology-related characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with two indicators
Perceived influence of border control technologies on anti-discrimination	PITAD	Technology-related characteristics	Single item
Uncertainty avoidance	UA	Cultural background	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Country	COUNTRY	User characteristics	Single item
Trust in border control authority	TIA	User characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with three indicators
Travel frequency (within the EU)	PTE1	User characteristics	Single item
General interest in technology	GIT	User characteristics	Latent construct (reflective) with four indicators

4.3.2.2 Model reliability and validity

Similar to the evaluation of previous models, α , ρ_c , and ρ_A were chosen as criteria for construct reliability. Table 6 presents reliability coefficients for PLS model 2 (single item measures omitted). For all constructs in the model, reliability coefficients are above the threshold 0.7, so reliability is at least acceptable for all constructs.

Table 6. Reliability of constructs in PLS model 2. Single item measures omitted.

Variable	α	ρ_c	ρ_A
BITU	0.963	0.976	0.963
EEOU	0.892	0.933	0.908
PE	0.872	0.921	0.880
EC	0.933	0.957	0.936

Variable	α	ρ_c	ρ_A
TIPT	0.886	0.946	0.886
EIOP	0.950	0.968	0.950
TIA	0.956	0.972	0.956
GIT	0.906	0.934	0.909
UA	0.909	0.943	0.911

Regarding validity, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} , and highest construct correlation for each construct are reported Table 7. Convergent validity is satisfactory as the AVE for all constructs exceeds the threshold of 0.5. Furthermore, the Fornell-Larcker criterion of discriminant validity is fulfilled as the \sqrt{AVE} is above the highest construct correlation in all cases.

Table 7. AVE and \sqrt{AVE} compared to highest construct correlations for PLS model 2. The Fornell-Larcker criterion is fulfilled when the \sqrt{AVE} for a constructs is higher than the highest construct correlation for this particular construct [29]. Single item measures omitted.

Variable	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}	Highest correlation	Variable of highest cor.	F.-L. crit. fulfilled
BITU	0.931	0.965	0.813	EC	Yes
EEOU	0.823	0.907	0.588	EC	Yes
PE	0.796	0.892	0.837	EC	Yes
EC	0.881	0.939	0.837	PE	Yes
TIPT	0.898	0.947	0.780	EC	Yes
EIOP	0.909	0.953	0.081	COUNTRY	Yes
TIA	0.920	0.959	0.657	TIPT	Yes
GIT	0.779	0.883	0.336	PE	Yes
UA	0.847	0.920	0.544	EC	Yes

4.3.2.3 Significance of model paths

Overall, PLS model 2 explains roughly 74% of the variance in BITU ($R^2 = 0.737$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.736$) indicating the model captures a high amount of relevant information present in the underlying dataset to predict BITU. Table 8 shows the bootstrapped coefficients for model paths in PLS model 2. All model paths are significant. The magnitude of associations does not differ much from PLS model 1. Generally, technology-related characteristics tend to have higher correlations with BITU, while links between user characteristics, cultural background and BITU tend to be smaller in magnitude. A more detailed interpretation of path coefficients is presented in the following section.

Table 8. Bootstrapped coefficients for paths in the PLS model 2.

Path	Bootstrap <i>M</i>	Bootstrap <i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	95% <i>CI</i>
EEOU → PE*	0.566	0.012	47.141	[0.542; 0.589]
EEOU → BITU*	0.034	0.010	3.298	[0.014; 0.055]
PE → BITU*	0.17	0.018	9.613	[0.135; 0.204]
EC → BITU*	0.377	0.020	19.037	[0.338; 0.416]
TIPT → BITU*	0.172	0.016	10.866	[0.141; 0.204]
EIOP → BITU*	-0.101	0.008	-12.663	[-0.116; -0.085]
TECH_3DFACE → BITU*	-0.026	0.009	-2.794	[-0.044; -0.008]
TECH_PASSPORT → BITU*	0.064	0.008	7.948	[0.048; 0.08]
TECH_FACE → BITU	0.007	0.009	0.787	[-0.01; 0.024]
TECH_EGATE → BITU*	0.046	0.008	5.587	[0.03; 0.062]
PITAD → BITU*	0.046	0.008	5.762	[0.03; 0.061]
COUNTRY_SWE → BITU*	-0.019	0.009	-2.069	[-0.037; -0.001]
COUNTRY_NOR → BITU	-0.007	0.008	-0.876	[-0.023; 0.009]
COUNTRY_ROM → BITU*	-0.044	0.009	-4.788	[-0.062; -0.026]
COUNTRY_EST → BITU	-0.021	0.009	-2.338	[-0.039; -0.003]
COUNTRY_GRE → BITU*	-0.05	0.009	-5.744	[-0.067; -0.033]
COUNTRY_FRA → BITU	-0.011	0.009	-1.205	[-0.029; 0.007]
COUNTRY_BEL → BITU	0.002	0.009	0.240	[-0.015; 0.019]
PTE1 → BITU*	-0.025	0.008	-3.046	[-0.041; -0.008]
TIA → BITU*	0.072	0.012	6.194	[0.049; 0.095]
GIT → BITU*	0.048	0.008	5.878	[0.032; 0.065]
UA → BITU*	0.034	0.010	3.353	[0.014; 0.053]

Note: *M* = mean, *SD* = standard Deviation, *t* = *t* statistic, *CI* = confidence interval. * $p < 0.05$

4.4 Model Interpretation

From an explanatory perspective, the PLS-based modelling provides insight in which factors be relevant for users' acceptance (respectively intention to use) smart border control technologies. For this interpretation the magnitude of path coefficients in Table 8 in are considered.

The most influential factors on BITU appear to fall into two broader categories: Factors related to efficiency and usefulness of the technology (EC, PE) and factors related to trust and privacy (TPIT, EIOP, TIA). EC appears to have the strongest association with BITU ($M_{bootstrapped} = 0.373$) followed by TPIT ($M_{bootstrapped} = 0.173$), PE ($M_{bootstrapped} = 0.170$), EIOP ($M_{bootstrapped} = 0.101$) and TIA ($M_{bootstrapped} = 0.072$) in descending order.

Path coefficients for TECH and COUNTRY indicate that there are small differences in the effect on BITU for certain technologies and countries. BITU tends to be lower in persons living in Sweden, Greece, and Romania compared to the reference category (Austria). Similarly, BITU tends to be lower for 3D face recognition and higher for e-gates and passport scanners in comparison to the reference category (fingerprint scanner). The magnitude of these difference appears to be small but still should be taken in account when deciding upon practical applications of smart border technologies.

Other variables that were identified as significant predictors of BITU are GIT, PITAD, EEOU, UUA and PTE1. This result indicates that persons that except high ease of use and a positive impact of border control technologies on anti-discrimination tend to report higher BITU. Similar positive relationships with BITU appear to exist for individuals with higher interest in technology and higher uncertainty avoidance. In contrast, persons that travel more often with the EU tend to report lower BITU based on PLS model 2. The effects of the aforementioned factors on BITU are generally rather small with $M_{bootstrapped}$ ranging from 0.026 to 0.049.

Finally, the model indicates that basic demographic attributes (gender, age, education) do not represent significant predictors of BITU. Similarly, two out of five variables related to the cultural background are not significantly associated with BITU (CO, MA). Moreover, PD and LTO were not included in the model in the first place as reliability and validity issues were identified regarding these variables. Figure 2 shows a graphical summary of the variables and relationships included in the PLS model 2 which was chosen as the final model.

Figure 2: Visual summary of the variables and relationships included in the final model (PLS model 2). Arrow thickness indicates magnitude of the respective path coefficient. For the categorical variables (TECH, COUNTRY) arrow thickness indicates the magnitude of the largest coefficient estimated among the respective binary factor levels (dummy-coded variables).

5 Reference Model (Machine-Learning-based)

This chapter presents the results of the training and evaluation of an alternative, machine-learning (ML) based model that is supposed to complement the main (PLS-SEM based) model presented in Chapter 4. To this end, after model development and evaluation, the ML modeling results are interpreted and compared to those of the PLS-SEM models from the previous chapter.

5.1 Background & Motivation

The ML based reference model should complement the main SEM-PLS model in two ways: firstly, it should serve as a reference benchmark for realistically achievable maximum prediction accuracy and secondly, it should provide additional information and insights on the dataset itself (e.g., by analyzing feature importances of the model, or by picking up different properties of the dataset).

Thus, since the reference model should primarily serve as prediction accuracy benchmark, the underlying algorithms should enable highest prediction performance levels for the given kind of data. To fulfil this requirement we chose XGBoost [30], a gradient-boosting algorithm that creates ensembles of decision-trees, as basis for our reference model. This choice is also motivated by the fact that XGBoost is widely known to outperform other common ML approaches (like deep learning), if training and test datasets are tabular by nature (see [31] and [32]). Furthermore, the resulting model (and the underlying datasets) can be interpreted to some extent, since XGBoost supports common explainability techniques such as LIME and SHAP [33].

5.2 Data preprocessing and analytical approach

In order to facilitate model comparison, the data for training and evaluation of the reference model was preprocessed in the same way as for the SEM model, as described in Section 4.2. The only difference was that for the reference model it was not necessary to dummy-code categorical variables.

As first step, an initial version of the reference model was developed using cross-validation and hyperparameter-optimization. Secondly, for subsequent comparison with the main model, the same model was trained and evaluated using the 80/20 train/test dataset described in Section 4.2, using the same features as listed in Table 1. For the machine-learning modeling itself, the XGBoost v1.6.1, Scikit-learn v1.1.2, Scikit-optimize v0.9.0, and Pandas v1.4.2 packages were used in a Python 3.9 environment.

5.3 Model Development and Evaluation

5.3.1 Model Development

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is an efficient open-source implementation of the gradient boosting algorithm for decision trees. XGBoost features parallel tree boosting for ensemble learning, which is based on combining multiple weak models to create a collectively strong machine-learning model. It is designed to be both computationally efficient and highly performant, and it can be used for classification and regression problems as well. It can automatically handle missing values, non-linear relationships and categorical features [30]. These advantageous properties and the fact that XGBoost is particularly suitable for tabular datasets (like the one serving as input for the envisaged traveler TAM model) (cf. [31], [32]) were the reasons for choosing XGBoost as underlying machine-learning algorithm for the reference model. The XGBRegressor of scikit-learn was used as algorithm implementation, using the factor BITU as target variable and proxy for technology acceptance.

Model training and evaluation in this first step was performed using 5-fold cross-validation, i.e. the dataset was randomly divided into five equally sized “folds”, of which one at a time was used as test set, while the other folds served as training set. For model evaluation in the context of the cross-validation, the following metrics were used: RMSE (root mean squared error), R^2 (coefficient of determination), and MAE (mean absolute error).

Since the XGBoost algorithm offers a range of hyper-parameters for tuning its performance, careful hyper-parameter optimization was required as first step in model development in order to obtain a representative reference model that fully exploits the capabilities of the chosen algorithm. To this end, we performed Bayesian Optimization of hyper-parameters which is known to be more efficient than traditional random or grid-based search.

Above procedure resulted in the following optimal parameters for the XGBRegressor: $\gamma = 4.7564300305 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $\text{learning_rate} = 0.0476586392$, $\text{max_depth} = 3$, $n_estimators = 420$, $\text{booster} = \text{'gbtree'}$. The resulting XGBoost model performance (based on 5-fold cross-validation) is the following:

Table 9: Evaluation results for the optimized XGBoost model. For each performance/error metric, average (mean) and standard deviation across the five cross-validation folds are presented.

Metric	Metric Value (mean)	Standard Deviation (of metric value)	Interpretation
R^2	0.741	0.023	Approx. 74% of variance can be explained by the model → very good (in the context of TAM modelling)
MAE	0.587	0.016	Small absolute error (prediction of BITU deviates from ground truth by 0.588 on average on a 7-point scale) → very good
RMSE	0.865	0.033	Fairly small mean-squared error → very good

The metric values of above error/performance metrics indicate a fairly high prediction performance achieved by the reference model (MAE and RMSE below 1, approx. 74% of the variance in the dataset can be explained). Very positively, these performance levels are stably achieved across different train/test splits (i.e., the model does not overfit), as suggested by the low standard deviations of above metrics across the different cross-validation folds.

All in all, these results mean that in the context of the traveller TAM dataset, high levels of model performance are achievable in principle (depending on the actual modelling approach algorithm used). At the same time, it is rather unlikely that a different modelling approach applied to bespoke dataset can achieve significantly higher performance levels.

5.4 Model Interpretation

Given the high accuracy of the tree-based reference model, it is also worth to interpret some of its properties. To this end, this section analyzes feature importance of the reference model using SHAP. SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), which is based on game-theoretic calculations, has become a highly popular approach for explaining single model predictions (local level) as well as feature importances and interactions (global level). Since the average SHAPley value of a feature directly expresses its impact on the target predictor variable, it has become a widely used, intuitively understandable approach for analyzing an model’s feature importances [33], [34].

As can be seen in Figure 3 below, the most important feature (and consequently: assumed determinant of acceptance) is EC (Expected Convenience), which impacts BITU prediction by approx. 0.6 scale units on average (on a seven-point scale). This is followed by PE (Performance Expectancy) and TIPT (Trust in Particular Technology) and other features - which however rapidly decrease in terms of their impact on model output.

This observation suggests that on overall, technology-related characteristics (i.e., in terms of how a person experiences the different aspects of a specific border control technology) seem to have more impact on acceptance than individual user-related characteristics (i.e., user attitudes, demographics and background).

Figure 3: Top 15 features in terms of feature importance calculated by SHAP. The more a feature impacts the model output variable (here: BITU), the more it is considered as important/influential.

5.5 Model Comparison

As next step, we compared the main SEM models (see Section 4.3) to the reference model with the goal to obtain a better understanding of their performance and identify eventual deviations in terms of e.g., key features used for prediction. To ensure a fair and valid comparison, all models were evaluated on behalf of the same train/test split of the modeling dataset (see Section 4.2) as well as the same error and performance metrics.

5.5.1 Performance Comparison

Table 10 below shows the performance of the main PLS-SEM models and the ML-based reference model in terms of RMSE and MAE. All models perform considerably better than a simple, constant dummy regressor that always suggests the BITU mean. The model comparison shows that the XGBoost reference model performs only slightly better than the PLS models in terms of absolute error. Regarding the practical relevance of the different error metrics, it is worth considering that larger deviations (e.g., predicting very high BITU for an individual with very low BITU) potentially have disproportionately higher negative impact in real-world scenarios. Thus, in practice, RMSE appears to be the preferable metric to consider as the RMSE gives higher weight to larger residuals (in contrast to

MAE). RMSEs for both the PLS model 2 and the reference model are similar, indicating equally high predictive capabilities for practical scenarios.

Table 10: Performance comparison of PLS SEM and reference model on behalf of RMSE, MAE and R^2 metrics.

Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2
PLS model 1b	0.893	0.614	0.708
PLS model 2	0.889	0.612	0.725
Reference model (XGBoost)	0.889	0.588	0.724
Dummy regressor (constant BITU mean)	1.703	1.394	0.000

Furthermore, an additional comparison of R^2 values shows that all models explain a similar amount of variance in BITU based on the test set ($R^2_{\text{PLS 1b}} = 0.708$, $R^2_{\text{PLS 2}} = 0.725$, $R^2_{\text{reference}} = 0.724$). Since the reference model serves as the benchmark in terms of realistically achievable model performance, above results suggest that the proposed TAM PLS-SEM models are highly complete and capture almost all relevant information present in the underlying dataset.

From a practical perspective, all models provide predictive capabilities that can be useful for predicting BITU in real-world scenarios. Given that the absolute error is approximately 0.6 on average on a 7-point scale, the model's predictions are likely to give a good indication of the behavioral intention to use smart border control technologies for a particular individual. As a hypothetical example, the model might predict a BITU value of 6.4 for a person that would report an actual BITU value of 7. Thus, the model would still predict the person to exhibited rather high BITU.

5.5.2 Feature Importance Comparison

In order to obtain a better understanding of commonalities and differences between main (PLS model 2) and reference model (XGBoost), we compared the feature importance rankings of the respective models (see Table 11 below), including also the features identified by the (more complex) PLS model 1b for the sake of completeness. As the comparison shows, all models largely agree on which input variables have the strongest impact on acceptance (as represented by the BITU target variable). They also agree almost fully on the ranking of the six most influential features. These results suggest that the reduced main model (PLS model 2) is truly fairly comprehensive in terms of having picked up all relevant information contained in the dataset, without having missed out on any relevant non-linearities or feature interactions that the ML-based reference model would have picked up.

Table 11: Comparison of most impactful features as identified by the main model (left) and reference model (right). The ranking of features for the PLS model is based on the estimated path coefficients. The ranking of features for the reference model is based on the mean SHAP values for the different features.

Model	PLS model 1b (full)	PLS model 2 (reduced)	Reference model (XGBoost)
Feature	EC	EC	EC
Importance	TIPT	TPIT	PE
Ranking	PE	PE	TPIT
(descending,	EIOP	EIOP	EIOP
i.e., the first	TIA	TIA	TIA
feature is the	TECH	TECH	TECH
	COUNTRY	COUNTRY	EEOU

most influential one)	GIT	GIT	GIT
	PITAD	PITAD	EIHW
	EEOU	EEOU	UA
	PTE1	UA	COUNTRY
	UA	PTE1	PSBC
	<i>CO</i> †		PITAD
	<i>DISCRIM</i> †		CO
	<i>AGE</i> †		MA

†Note: features CO, DISCRIM and AGE are not considered as being statistically significant by PLS model 1b and are listed here for reference only.

6 Model Deployment and Prediction Aspects

6.1 SEM vs. ML-based Approach

Among others, the comparison results show that the ML-based reference model performs better than the main SEM model in terms of prediction accuracy (albeit to a very small degree only). Thus, the reader might wonder whether it might not be preferable to use the reference model for the ETAP acceptance prediction module instead of the main model.

The answer to this question is that in general, such a decision depends on the overall requirements posed by application domain and purpose of the system: If prediction accuracy would be the only criterion, then the reference model would be hypothetically the better option. However, as discussed in section 5.5, while the MAE is slightly lower for the reference model, the RMSE is the same for the PLS model 2 and the reference model. As the RMSE is the preferable metric in practical scenarios (also see section 5.5), both models appear to be equally well suited for practical application in terms of predictive performance. Moreover, since the METICOS platform is supposed to serve as mission-critical decision-support system operating in a sensitive domain (border control), prediction accuracy is only one out of a range of relevant requirements (see Chapter 2). For example, the model must not be a black box, since the model and its predictions have to be fully explainable, leaving the possibility to identify and gaps or biases. The SEM-based main model is fully transparent and explainable (thanks to being based on directly interpretable structural equations), as opposed to the ML-based reference model, which can be explained to some extent only (with the help of additional tools such as LIME or SHAP). Furthermore, a SEM model can be manually altered and extended with additional equations and factors in order to incorporate domain knowledge, if required. A SEM model also reflects theoretical underpinnings and hypotheses which inform its model structure, which again allows for a more controlled and understandable model development as compared to purely data-driven approaches such as decision trees (which the reference model is based on). Moreover, PLS encompasses a sound foundation in measurement theory while alternative methods must rely on naïve sum or mean scores which might be associated with severe limitations [16].

Given the above reasons and the observed minor performance differences, the PLS-SEM based main model (PLS model 2) remains the preferred approach in the context of METICOS.

6.2 Handling of Potential Biases in Model and Dataset

6.2.1 Background on Biases in Quantitative Modelling

In various fields it is observed that ML models generally deliver superior performance compared with conventional, deterministic algorithms. However, they are considered by most as black boxes, which

are hard, if not impossible, to interpret. Thus, there is growing concern about the potential to reproduce discrimination against a particular group of people based on protected characteristics such as gender, race, cultural background, or other. Algorithms trained on biased data are prone to learn, perpetuate or even reinforce these biases [35].

Numerous different ways have been identified to detect the presence of bias regarding protected or sensitive attributes (including age, gender, race, cultural background etc.), while there are various definitions for fairness and bias proposed by academia [36].

Beyond merely identifying biases, various bias mitigation strategies have been proposed in literature developed in recent years, which can be divided in the following three distinct groups. Efficient bias mitigation starts at the data acquisition and processing phase since the source of the data and also the extraction methods can introduce unwanted bias. Algorithms which belong to the *pre-processing* family ensure that the input data is balanced and fair. This can be achieved by suppressing the protected attributes, by changing class labels of the data set, and by reweighting or resampling the data. For instance, when there is an imbalance regarding different age groups (i.e., high variation in the number of samples in different age groups), a stratification strategy might be required (e.g., by oversampling the most underrepresented group). For the second type of mitigation strategies, the *in-processing* algorithms, undesired bias is mitigated during the training phase. A straightforward approach is to integrate a fairness penalty directly in the loss function. The final group of mitigation algorithms follows a *post-processing* approach, where only the output of a trained classifier is modified.

6.2.2 Potential Biases in the Traveler TAM Dataset

As regards the purpose and use case of the TAM models developed in this deliverable (prediction and explanation of likely acceptance of specific border control technology by a traveler), the most relevant potential biases relate to predictions based on a given persons demographics, identity and background. In the case of METICOS WP5, this can happen mainly due to a) imbalanced distribution or b) underrepresentation of user groups/segments in the dataset used. In the following, we are going to discuss potential biases in the concrete case of modelling the METICOS traveller TAM, using the most critical variables “Sex”, “Age” and “Education” as representative examples.

In the case of “Sex”, the traveller survey dataset is well balanced between male and female (for a more detailed analysis and charts, see D5.2 Section 4.3). However, the “diverse” segment is heavily underrepresented in the traveller dataset (0.66%) because of limited availability of this demographic. Therefore, deployments using the resulting model have to be limited to making predictions for male/female people only.

In the case of “Age”, the dataset categorizes people into three different age groups of which groups 1 (young) and 2 (mid-aged) are balanced, but the third group (65+) has approx. 50% less samples than the other two (due to limited availability of certain demographics, see D5.2). In this case, a stratification strategy would be required for rebalancing age groups, (e.g., by oversampling group 3).

In the case of “Education”, the panel distribution is likely to be skewed towards academics (albeit to unknown extent, see the respective discussion in D5.2). This again can be compensated by rebalancing the different groups by resampling, for example.

However, in the concrete case of modeling the METICOS traveler TAM, none of the above variables (or other demographics) have been found to be significant for prediction and thus are not used as feature in the final models. Therefore, we conclude that only the application of the debiasing measures for “Sex” are required for models based on the traveler TAM dataset at hand.

6.2.3 Outlook: Systematic Handling of Biases in Upcoming Datasets

While minimal bias mitigation measures are required for the traveler dataset and the corresponding PLS model, it is important to further explore systematic strategies for bias identification and mitigation regarding future datasets and models.

Further systematic analysis regarding identification of bias in addition to bias mitigation of the METICOS TAM models and underlying respective datasets, will be performed as part of METICOS WP7 and more specifically Task 7.5. In particular, for the Cross-Sectorial Big Data Analytics component, one of the objectives is to observe how well a model built on a given dataset generalize to a different dataset, thus, is equally applicable to test the demographic representativeness of datasets.

In particular, in Task 7.5, we take the following steps when evaluating the data and models for bias: Comparison of the frequency of missing values for certain features across different groups, evaluation of the distribution of the target for different groups in the data, and finally using different tests, as proposed by literature, identification of examples of bias in the data or model predictions. For our case in WP7, we aim to ensure that samples include diversity and equal representation to avoid racial, gender, ethnic and age discrimination, measure accuracy levels separately for different demographic categories to see whether unfairness exists in any group and audit models for accuracy and fairness.

For implementing strategies for bias identification and mitigation as part of WP7, we will be using the AI Fairness 360 toolkit¹, developed by IBM. This toolkit is an extensible open-source library containing techniques developed by the research community to help detect and mitigate bias in models throughout the AI application lifecycle (including pre-processing, in-processing and post-processing approaches). Being available in both Python and R, the AI Fairness 360 package includes a comprehensive set of metrics for datasets and models to test for biases, explanations for these metrics, and algorithms to mitigate bias in datasets and models. The results of this analysis, applicable bias identification and mitigation strategies, and respective models will be reported as part of D7.6.

¹ <https://aif360.mybluemix.net/>

7 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the development of an empirical model to explain and predict a traveler's intention to use a given smart border control technology. PLS-SEM was chosen as the most appropriate methodological approach as it is not only more robust, but it also combines a theoretically sound explanatory perspective and predictive capabilities, thereby overcoming the limitations of traditional SEM approaches typically being used in acceptance modeling.

The final PLS model (i.e., reduced PLS-SEM model, see Section 4.3.2) provides insight into the key factors that influence BITU. The most influential factors on BITU appear to fall into two broader categories: variables related to efficiency and usefulness on the one hand and variables related to trust and privacy on the other. Moreover, basic demographic characteristics (gender, age, education) do not show impactful associations with BITU.

To evaluate the predictive capabilities of the final PLS model, its out-of-sample performance was compared to a reference model that is based on a purely machine learning-based approach (see Section 5.5). Results show that the PLS model achieves similarly good predictive performance on new data in comparison to the ML-based reference model. Both models provide predictive capabilities with high practical usefulness. However, the PLS model also has a sound foundation in measurement theory and its results and decisions are more transparent and explainable. Thus, the PLS model is the preferred model in the context of the METICOS project.

For the remaining activities of the METICOS project, the results presented in this deliverable are going to be used in the following ways. Firstly, the resulting traveler PLS-SEM TAM model serves as the basis of the ETAP algorithm development in T5.5. Furthermore, once the border control staff survey is completed and results data analyzed (T5.2), the same modeling approach as presented here will be used for the development of the staff TAM model, which will be reported upon in deliverable D5.8.

8 References

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